

Statistical Aspects of Fibre and Bundle Strength in Hybrid Composites

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ABSTRACT

Tests have been carried out on single carbon fibres, impregnated tows of the same fibre, and similar tows made up into a glass-carbon fibre hybrid laminate. The measured strengths of the carbon-fibre have been analysed on the basis of a Weibull distribution. It has been shown that, over the range of gauge-lengths used, the impregnated tows and the hybrids were stronger than the single fibres, but did not behave as ideal Weibull solids.

INTRODUCTION

The strength of many brittle materials may be shown to be related to the bulk of the test sample. In the case of strong fibres, such as glass and carbon, the strength of a single fibre is a function of the length tested. It follows that the strength of a fibre composite, or array of fibres, will be some function of that of the single fibre involving a consideration of bulk, i.e. the length and number of fibres in the element in question. The objective of this work has been to reconcile the observed statistical distribution of strengths in single carbon-fibres, impregnated tows of fibre and similar tows in a hybrid glass/carbon laminate.

The experimental programme was conducted on fibres drawn from a single tow of 1000 high strength carbon filaments. Single fibre, impregnated tows and hybrid specimens were tested in tension to give strength data at several gauge lengths. These data have been subjected to an order-statistics analysis and tested against a simple Weibull two parameter model.

EXPERIMENTAL

Single Fibre Tests

Fibres were selected at random from a length of 1000 filament, high strength carbon-fibre tow (Celion 1000). They were mounted on standard "window" cards, cut to give gauge lengths of 50, 20, 10 and 1 mm and were tested in tension on an Instron machine fitted with a 0.5N capacity load cell at an extension rate of 0.1 mm/min. Seventy repeat tests were conducted at each length. The diameter of each fibre was measured by laser diffraction to an accuracy of $\pm 2\%$.

Impregnated Tow Tests

Specimens were prepared by vacuum impregnating lengths of the 1000 filament tow with a liquid epoxy resin (Shell 828 cured with NMA and K61B), they were cured, hanging in an air circulating oven at 100°C and then post-cured at 130°C. They were cut to give specimens with gauge lengths of 300, 150, 50 and 20 mm which were then tensile tested (30 specimens at each gauge length). The total fibre cross-section in the tow was calculated from the average fibre diameter obtained from the 260 single filament tests. The actual mean tow diameter was 0.31 mm corresponding to a fibre volume fraction of 0.67.

Hybrid Tests

These specimens were made by incorporating a single tow of the carbon into a uniaxial glass-fibre/epoxy resin laminate (fig.1). Six lengths of carbon tow were laid onto a 300 mm square metal frame, spaced at intervals of approximately 30 mm. E-glass fibre roving was then wound onto the frame, over the carbon to form a sandwich array. This was then vacuum impregnated with the same epoxy resin used for the impregnated tows, cured and post cured as above. Precautions were taken to ensure that the carbon tows remained straight and parallel to the glass rovings. The resulting plate was then cut up into 10 mm wide coupons with the carbon tows centrally located as depicted in fig.1. A cross section showing the carbon tow is shown in fig.2, the tow diameter was approximately 0.3 mm.

HYBRID SPECIMEN GEOMETRY

Fig 1.

CROSS SECTION

Fig 2. Cross section of hybrid test piece.

Aluminium end tags were bonded to the coupons to give a total gauge length of 220 mm. An electrical resistance strain gauge was attached to the middle of the test section. The glass fibre and resin system chosen for these test pieces gave a highly transparent laminate so that the carbon tow was clearly visible to the naked eye and under the low-power optical microscope.

The test piece was extended in tension in an Instron machine at a rate of 0.05 mm/min, force and strain were recorded on an X-Y recorder whilst a second pen was coupled to a potentiometric device which was used to indicate the position, along the gauge length, of an internal carbon-tow fracture. As the test progressed a fracture would occur in the carbon tow (which has a much smaller strain to fracture than the glass); each fracture event was easily detected audibly and its position could be seen through the transparent glass-epoxy. The indicator device was aligned with each such fracture and thus the force, strain, and position of each event was recorded. For the purposes

of the analysis a nominal 200 mm gauge length was selected (to avoid end effects) and all fractures within this length were recorded. The test was terminated when the crack spacing approached 10 mm, when the strain was typically 2%. This is a refinement of the techniques described by Manders and Bader (1). Eleven specimens were tested.

The data were analysed by a computer programme in which the 200 mm gauge portion on the test piece was notionally divided into sub-gauge lengths of 2 x 100, 4 x 50, and 10 x 20 mm. Each of these gauge lengths was then treated as an independent test piece. Thus, in the case of the first fracture observed in a test piece, the strength of the tow was calculated from the observed failure strain and this was designated the strength of that 200 mm length; it would also be the strength of the weaker of the two 100 mm lengths, the weakest of the four 50 mm lengths and so on. The process was then repeated with the programme selecting each gauge length in turn and finding the fracture with the lowest failure strain in that gauge length. It should be noted that the measured parameter was the strain at fracture and that the stress was calculated from this by applying the Young's modulus of the carbon fibre as determined by a separate test on an impregnated tow. There is an assumption of strain uniformity throughout the test piece. The crack position was determined to within ± 1 mm from a datum, which was one end of the 200 mm gauge length, corrected according to the strain at the time of observation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Weibull (2) has proposed a simple distribution function which may be applied to many materials phenomena. The integrated form of the two parameter version is:

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^w \right] \quad \text{----(1)}$$

Where $F(\sigma)$ is the cumulative distribution function (c.d.f.) of the variable σ (which in this case will be the strength), σ_0 is the "characteristic value" of strength, w is the "Weibull modulus". The Weibull modulus is an inverse measure of the variability of σ , and σ_0 is a normalising parameter which renders the function dimensionless. The c.d.f. is a description of the observed strength values when ordered from the lowest to the highest. This is equivalent to a probability of failure ranging from 0 to 1.

The probability of survival of a fibre of unit length may be written:

$$P_s = \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^w \right] \quad \text{----(2)}$$

The characteristic stress σ_0 is thus the stress corresponding to $P_s = \frac{1}{e}$ (i.e. 0.368 or $P_f = 0.632$).

And that of a fibre of length l by:

$$P_s = \exp \left[- l \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^w \right] \quad \text{----(3)}$$

The quantity l is a "weakest-link" scaling factor. In order to test the correlation between experimental values and the Weibull model it is convenient to plot the data on logarithmic axes. $l n \sigma$ is plotted against $l n l n [1/(1-P_f)]$ which should yield a straight line of slope w according to the equation:

$$l n l n [1/(1-P_f)] = w l n \sigma - w l n \sigma_0 + l n l \quad \text{----(4)}$$

The P_f curves for single fibres, impregnated tows and hybrids are shown in figs. 3 and 4 and the associated logarithmic plots in figs. 5 and 6. Figures 7 and 8 are expanded forms of the curves shown in fig. 6. A summary of the data is given in Table 1.

TABLE I

	Gauge length (mm)	Number of observations	Mean strength $\bar{\sigma}$ (GPa)	σ_0 (GPa)	C.V. of σ	w	w^*
SINGLE FIBRES	50	66	2.25	2.41	18.4	6.1	6.1
	20	70	2.45	2.63	19.9	5.6	
	10	64	3.05	3.25	20.2	5.7	
	1	57	4.24	4.53	19.9	5.7	
IMPREGNATED	300	29	2.56	2.60	6.80	16	27
	150	32	2.68	2.77	7.17	15	
TOWS	50	30	2.81	2.87	6.02	18	19
	20	28	2.82	2.90	5.49	19	
HYBRIDS	200	11	3.60	3.69	4.04	23	45
	100	22	3.67	3.75	3.88	27	
	50	44	3.73	3.78	3.88	29	
	20	109	3.79	3.85	3.55	33	

* Derived from the slopes of lines in fig. 10.

The σ vs P_f curves in fig.3 clearly show the variations in strength associated with the four gauge lengths. The mean strength and the range both increase as the gauge length is reduced. The same data are displayed in fig. 5 with the line of best fit drawn through each set. A reasonable fit is observed in 3 of the 4 cases and the lines are approximately parallel with slopes lying between 5.6 and 6.1. This approximates to the prediction of the Weibull model and we take the average value for the Weibull modulus, w , to be 5.8. This falls within the range quoted by other workers (1,3). If the scaling factor is incorporated into the model (equation 3) we may also predict the relative displacement of the lines on the stress axis. In Table 2a we compare the observed characteristic stress, σ_0 , with that predicted by weakest link scaling of the 50 mm gauge length data. Again the experimental values are seen to fall quite close to those predicted, indicating that the fibres exhibit weakest link behaviour. We are unable to offer any explanation for the somewhat anomalous results at the 10 mm gauge length.

The results for both the impregnated and the hybrid tests are given in figs. 4 and 6. The stress values in these figures have been calculated on the basis of the total carbon-fibre cross section and may thus be compared directly with the single fibre data. It may be seen that they follow the same general form as figs. 3 and 5 in that, in each case, the strength is observed to increase as the gauge length is reduced. The range however is much narrower than that for the single fibres and does not show the pronounced increase with decreasing gauge length. It may be noted that the range of single fibre strength values overlaps those of both the impregnated tows and the hybrids. At a fixed gauge length however the mean strength of the impregnated bundle is greater than that of the single fibre and the hybrid is even stronger. The strength of both sets of bundles is much less sensitive to gauge length than that of the single fibres. These observations are reflected in the values for the Weibull modulus calculated from the data and tabulated in Table 1. The mean value of w for the impregnated tows is 17 and for the hybrids 28. The values for w do however vary quite considerably over the different gauge lengths, much more than for the single fibre data. This is apparent from the slopes of the lines in figs. 7 and 8. In the case of the hybrid material there appears to be a trend towards a higher Weibull modulus at shorter gauge lengths. A similar trend is seen for three of the four lengths of the impregnated bundles but there is one anomalous set at 150 mm gauge length. If this observation is correct it means that neither type of bundle meets the strength/length relationship implicit in the Weibull model. This is in contrast to the behaviour of the single fibres where w is almost constant over the four gauge lengths. On the other hand when we apply weakest link scaling to the data a good fit is observed in all cases (Table 2b,2c).

TABLE 2

	Gauge Length (mm)	Characteristic stress σ_0 (GPa)		Difference (%)
		Measured	Predicted by "weakest-link" scale	
a. <u>SINGLE FIBRES</u>	50	2.41	2.41	0
	20	2.63	2.80	+6.5%
	10	3.25	3.22	-1.0%
	1	4.53	4.65	+2.5%
b. <u>IMPREGNATED TOWS</u>	300	2.60	2.60	0
	150	2.77	2.76	-0.5%
	50	2.87	2.90	+1.0%
	20	2.90	2.98	+2.5%
c. <u>HYBRIDS</u>	200	3.69	3.69	0
	100	3.75	3.93	+5%
	50	3.78	3.85	+2%
	20	3.85	3.76	-2%

The impregnated tows showed classic elastic/brittle failure characteristics. There was no deviation from linearity in the force/displacement trace, when failure occurred they often broke into several fragments and sometimes split longitudinally. It was not possible to identify the position of the primary tensile failure. In the hybrid specimens, individual tow failures were observed as sudden events. Their position was easily seen through the transparent glass-epoxy and debonding was observed either side of the transverse fracture path. This debonded region extended for approximately 1.5 mm either side of the crack path. The debonded length appeared to increase with applied stress. Fig. 9 is an optical photomicrograph of a section through the failure zone. The individual fractures of the carbon fibres can be seen, these are spread over about 1 mm along the length of the tow at each failure point.

A simplistic approach to the strength of a bundle of fibres, is to consider that the probability of encountering a critical flaw in a bundle of n fibres of length l is the same as in a single fibre of length nl . The probability of failure could then be considered to be a function of fibre volume, rather than length, and the concept could be extended to bulk composites. If that single critical flaw caused the bundle to fail then the strength of both single fibres and bundles could be expressed on a fibre volume basis. A bundle would always be weaker than a single fibre of similar length. This might well be the case for bundles containing only a few filaments, especially if the variability of strength were also low (i.e. high Weibull modulus). In these cases when the first fibre break occurs the remaining fibres would be overloaded and fail as a consequence of the first break. In larger bundles the load intensification on fibre failure is less and, when the strength variability is high, a greater proportion of the fibres are stronger and are, thus, capable of bearing the higher stress. We observe that the mean strength of both the impregnated and hybrid tows is greater than that of the single fibres at similar gauge lengths. In these materials the presence of the matrix resin localises the extent of stress redistribution around individual single fibre breaks, and failure of the bundle will occur only when several fibre breaks interact to precipitate the final failure sequence. In fig. 10 the mean strengths of the fibres and bundles are plotted on a volume basis. In this l_n/l_n plot the mean values of strength for each set are linear and the slope of those lines is equal to $-1/w$. In this case the derivation of w is from the whole set of data rather than the individual gauge lengths. (These values are given in the final column of Table 1). There is good agreement for the single fibres, but the fit is less satisfactory for the impregnated tows and the hybrids. The lines in fig. 10 converge and would intersect at a volume corresponding to a single fibre of gauge length somewhat less than 1 mm. At volumes greater than this the bundles and hybrids are stronger than the single fibre and vice-versa. Manders et al (4)

Fig. 3

Fig. 5

Fig. 4

Fig. 6

Plots of P_f vs. Strength for single fibres and bundles.

Weibull plots of data from figs. 3 and 4.

Fig. 7

Fig. 9 Longitudinal section through tow failure

Fig. 8

Expanded Weibull plots from fig.6.

Fig. 10. Mean strength vs. fibre volume plots for all materials compared.

have conducted a computer simulation of the strength of both dry and impregnated bundles of fibres of a range of Weibull moduli using two different load sharing rules. Under the universal load sharing rule, the load shed by a broken fibre is shared equally between all other (unbroken) fibres in the bundle, whereas under the local load sharing rule only the nearest neighbours participate. They find in both cases, at the ineffective length, the bundles should be weaker than the fibres. We do not know the ineffective length for single fibres but there is some evidence from optical microscopy (1) that it is of the order of 100 μm for single carbon fibres of 8 μm diameter.

The actual load sharing mechanism and the ineffective length are of vital importance in determining the relative strength of the bundle, since these will determine how many interacting fibre breaks are necessary for failure initiation and will also determine the interaction distance. As fibre variability increases (w decreases), it is to be expected that the number of breaks required to initiate failure would increase. Batdorf has proposed (5) that the number of local fibre breaks required to fail a bundle is given by the ratio of Weibull modulus of the bundle to that of the fibre. In the present work this suggests about 3 breaks for the impregnated tows and 5 for the hybrids.

We cannot, at present, offer a quantitative explanation for the higher strength observed in the hybrid bundles. There is a small effect due to the thermal mismatch between the carbon and the glass fibres, but the main effect appears to be a stress redistribution between the carbon and the surrounding glass reinforced material.

CONCLUSIONS

The strength distribution observed in single carbon fibres tested at gauge lengths ranging from 1 - 50 mm shows good agreement with a weakest-link scaled, two-parameter Weibull distribution. The Weibull modulus was 5.8 which is in general agreement with other work on single fibres.

Impregnated tows of 1000 filaments of the same fibre at gauge lengths of 20-300 mm had higher mean strengths than the single fibres at similar gauge lengths. There was reasonable conformity to the Weibull distribution for tests at the same gauge length, but w appeared to increase with decreasing gauge length. A similar trend was observed in the hybrid bundles which were significantly stronger than the impregnated tows and had higher Weibull moduli. These results would seem to confirm the existence of a hybrid effect where the carbon-fibre tow is stronger when surrounded by glass fibre reinforced material.

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